

English Education for Academic Excellence: Communication and Soft Skills

Kamil Kalandar Nadaf

Assistant Professor of English, Shikshanmaharshi Dr. Bapuji Salunkhe College, Miraj

Corresponding Author – Kamil Kalandar Nadaf

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18978623

Abstract:

English has become the most important language of the world. No one is fair from its influence, full stop it is acting as a link language between the different non-English backgrounds linguistically. Bringing the world together and making it more like a global village. English has established itself as a lingua franca. English education is one of the most important aspects in the education system around the globe. English is expanding day by day the most important aspects for the workforce. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is an important technique in that regard along with Task Based Learning (TBL) to engage students and peers in various activities to impart and foster the language skill in them and by that help them to achieve great aims in their academic life by enhancing their academic excellence.

Keywords: *Link language, lingua franca, education system, CLT, TBL, academic excellence.*

Introduction:

Bharatratna Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar said about English that, 'English is a tigress's milk'. This can be seen in our everyday life. A person who speaks and writes proficiently in English is held in high regard in any institution. English has established itself as world's most spoken language due to its flexible nature (linguistically) and power of assimilation (adding words from various languages) English is becoming rich both linguistically and by new words adding in it each day that is the reason English education is made in world's almost every country education system. Learning the English language is seen as the way of personality development. It is considered that knowledge of English boosts confidence and gives the sense of self-worth to its user. That is why English education is not just an education these days but a way to excel in both academic and professional life.

English as Lingua franca:

Former lingua franca Greek and Latin were replaced by English many years ago and it is continuing to do so even today in other languages. Most of the world is using English, if not entirely. English has become a backbone of communication, dissemination of knowledge, global discourse, the research field, the field of Higher Education etc. The inclusivity of literature extended due to use of English for the medium of writing. People who are readers from various backgrounds can be catered to through this.

British imperialism is the major reason why the English became common in most of the parts of the world. Their purposeful efforts to make the non-English speaking natives to speak and communicate in English have given the English the status it has today. Macaulay's, 'downward filtration theory' is one of the famous examples of how they did it.

In Academics it has become easy with the help of English to generalise the finding and get acknowledgement and appreciation from the

larger part of the world. The dissemination of knowledge through English has become the new way of civilizing. It is breaking the barriers of language, countries'(non-English speaking), culture and ideologies to reach more and more people. English language skills which are LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing) are useful in understanding the different scholarly texts, academic studies and it gives opportunities to participate in discussion to produce a scholarly work together like Francis Bacon said, 'Reading Makes a ready man, writing makes a perfect man and conference makes an exact man.'

English as a link language:

Both internationally and nationally we see that English is acting as a bridge between the speakers from different language backgrounds. My personal experience about the usability of English as a linked language occurred to me when I was in Karnataka. I was saved by English because many people from there were not able to speak in the national language Hindi. This is when English acts as a primary language for communication. The importance of English has been greatly understood by our national leaders also. When we defeated the foreign yoke and attained freedom many had advice to completely abolish the use of English in new India. But our first and visionary Prime Minister of India Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru said about the English language that, 'we should not throw the baby out with the bath water.' Meaning the bath water is Britisher and due to their presence and governance in India cultural and linguistic assimilation has occurred helped to establish a new community who intends to use English for advancement.

Skill imparted through English education:

Like every language, English also has four basic skills which are listening, speaking, and writing. When we achieve rashtriy Hindi

skills then and only then can we say that we have achieved proficiency in that language. Our education system always focuses on these skills development in the students. But apart from that the demand of the hour is communicative English and with that the Excellency in soft skills is also taking a center stage in the education system.

Many methods are prevalent in education to impart the English language skills in students. Now it is necessary to focus on communicative English and soft skills development also. Communicative English teaching leads to communicative competence in students which is not limited to just linguistic knowledge but it focuses on sociolinguistics which is a much-needed skill in a country like India where people from various cultural backgrounds are coming together in the education system and in the real-world scenario. Also, it is a more beneficial (communicative English education) because it provides a pragmatic platform for students to practice how they will converse or communicate in the real world. It will give them space to try, test, and sharpen their strategic abilities to use the language carefully, meaningfully, and proficiently.

Along with that the most demanded skill set in any work nowadays is not just hard skills but soft skills also. Soft skills are not just learned but earned and sharpened by practice. It is interpersonal and intrapersonal skill, intrapersonal like leadership, emotional intelligence, critical thinking adaptability etc. and interpersonal competency like teamwork. These skills are much needed for academic excellence due to its collaborative nature. These skills provide a way to present ourselves and by that attain desired professional success.

Enhancing communicative English language skills:

CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) is a very useful model of teaching to improve communicative English in students. It is useful to promote interactive and meaningful English in a classroom environment. It is majorly focused on learners' engagement. It allows students to communicate between them in a safer environment under the guidance of the teacher. This method includes the real-life based tasks to make students acquainted with the real-life scenarios and negotiation of meanings is done. Through that, soft skills like problem solving and collaboration are also developed.

Four language skills must be taught in integration with the communicative English language teaching. Because of that the learning of communicative English can become interactive and the same goes for the language skills. The isolated learning environment is a major obstacle in acquiring both language and communicative English skills. Another approach is learner centered activity to encourage them to take part. This will boost their confidence and give them enthusiasm to do activities more cheerfully.

There are various exercises that educators can adopt. As an instructor educator must clarify that the focus of the activity is on meaningful communication rather than accuracy. Educators can construct the real-life events in which students are more comfortable to use the English language which is all done in a safer classroom environment. This simulative activity will focus on their selection of dialogues, the role they choose to play and the information they convey. Between their communication the communication gap can also be identified and understood. This activity can be useful to enhance fluency and check the meaning negotiated in that conversation which holds equal importance in communicative English as grammar knowledge.

Communication can be fostered through the communicative tasks which are discussion. In which the group of students discusses certain points by learning to listen, interpret and respond to the views presented by another group member. This will be beneficial to enhance communicative language skills along with language skill. The activity which encourages group activity like giving some tasks to do in groups which is a project. This gives students an opportunity to communicate between peers of their groups. After the activity, taking the feedback can be beneficial for both the learner and the teacher. Feedback assures to reinforce the fluency in language, clarity in conversation and sociolinguistic ability in general in participating students.

Enhancing soft skills through English education:

In multi-cultural society like India demands from its civilians to functioning the machinery of state smoothly and along with that assurance that the individuals progress in Academics and professional career also will happen side by side this could be attended by keeping healthy environment at society and workplace where soft skills are much needed. Fostering of soft skills starts at school level where educators act as an instructor and facilitator while organising the activities for the students.

TBL (Task Based Learning) is a prominent way to educate the students while enhancing their soft skills. All language learning revolves around language skills. TBL provides an additional edge in the process of language acquisition. Various activities can be organised which provides a way for learners to engage in the tasks to learn English effectively. Educators' tasks as an instructor and facilitator educator must guide the students to use authentic language; this could be done in the context of planning of events, solving certain problems etc. Teachers' role is important because

it is teachers' responsibility to provide scaffolding and not to be merely a transmitter of knowledge.

Various activities are there that could be used to foster and enhance soft skills in students along with language skills. Role plays are important both for communicative English and to embed soft skills in students. Role plays assign the students a certain role which is related to their day-to-day life. They decide the dialogue and the room for improvisation gives the relevance to the real world. This enhances real world communication and eventually makes them capable of problem solving. To enhance the soft skills is another activity that is useful is group projects. As a mentor educator should assign a group of students a certain activity on which they can contribute. While making the group teachers should make the group of students from different cultural backgrounds. As a facilitator educator facilitates and mentors the students to encourage them to plan their work, assign their roles, the extensive research done by the students, preparing or drafting a project and presenting it collaboratively. This will lead to faster attendance to work in groups from the peers of different cultural and linguistic backgrounds.

Another activity that is considered highly beneficial to enhance soft skills is debates and public speaking. These activities can be organised both in classroom and out of the classroom. This is an activity in which students present their views on certain topics in which they learn to respect the views of other participants and present their views in a polite manner. The role of educator must be as a guide and facilitator. This activity builds confidence in using the English language and provides an opportunity to students to present themselves. This activity enhances clarity and sharpens the students' argumentative skills. This is also beneficial to promote critical thinking in the students.

Various soft skills are embedded, fostered, and enhanced through these activities adopted in English education. The language skills and shop skills are both important in holistic development of learners to excel in both academic and professional life. Activities like pair work group projects and learning tasks done in cooperation between students foster soft skills like teamwork and collaboration. By comparing their view points during debates and public speaking it provides a way to listen, interpret and present their views about the issue that has been presented in front of them. This kind of activity enhances critical thinking in students. The activities like group discussion and group projects along with their role assigned by the teacher during those activities foster and enhance various soft skills in those students majorly they are the skills of taking initiative and active participation as a leader. Activities like role plays and the various moments in those role plays to improvise and present their views fosters in the students the sense of self confidence and ability to express themselves. Interpersonal and intrapersonal both kinds of communication help to embed these various kinds of soft skills which are highly demanded in academic and professional life.

Conclusion:

English education is not merely teaching grammar and literature; it is a tool to make the student ready for the challenges they are going to face in the real world. These soft skills are held at the same level of importance as hard skills if not more. That is why to make the students ready for society and make or convert them into an asset to a country's progress, it is essential to embed knowledge of English communicative language and soft skills to support this. Without these skills our education will become the shelf-filler and not the beneficial factor for our society.

References:

1. Brown, H. Douglas. *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. Pearson Education, 2007.
2. Larsen-Freeman, Diane. *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press, 2000.
3. Nation, I. S. P., and Jonathan Newton. *Teaching ESL/EFL Listening and Speaking*. Routledge, 2009.
4. Richards, Jack C. *Communicative Language Teaching Today*. Cambridge University Press, 2006.
5. Willis, Dave, and Jane Willis. *Tasks for Language Teachers*. Cambridge University Press, 2007.